

Pedagogical approaches to the development of artistic thinking of students.**Ibatova Nigora Istamovna**

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Annotatsiya. Maqolada badiiy va obrazli fikrlashni rivojlantirishdagi muammolar, badiiy va obrazli tafakkurning rivojlanish jarayonini tadqiq etib tushunishga hissa qo'shgan va butun dunyo bo'ylab ta'lim nazariyasi va amaliyotiga katta ta'sir ko'rsatgan tadqiqotchilar yoritilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Strategiya, innovatsiya, art-terapist, intellekt, vizual-fazoviy, komponent, sub'yektiv, ob'yektiv, individual-psixologik, individual-tipologik.

Abstract. The article highlights the problems in the development of artistic and figurative thinking, the researchers who contributed to the research and understanding of the development process of artistic and figurative thinking and had a great influence on the theory and practice of education around the world.

Key words: Strategy, innovation, art therapist, intellect, visual-spatial, component, subjective, objective, individual-psychological, individual-typological.

Development of artistic and figurative thinking is an important pedagogical problem that requires attention in the educational system. Artistic and imaginative thinking involves the ability to create unique ideas and perspectives and express them in an aesthetically pleasing manner.

One of the challenges in developing artistic and visual thinking is that it encourages more students to take a different approach to teaching and learning than traditional methods that emphasize memorization and conformity—that is, exploration, experimentation, and risk-taking. requires a focused approach.

To promote artistic and imaginative thinking, teachers should provide opportunities for students to participate in open-ended projects, encourage collaboration and peer feedback, and use a range of artistic media materials must implement strategies such as ensuring access. It should be noted that the development of artistic and figurative thinking is not limited to art. These skills can be used in a number of fields including science, technology, engineering and mathematics (STEM). By incorporating artistic and figurative thinking into the curriculum, students are challenged can develop the skills and thinking needed to solve problems and create innovative solutions.

Many researchers have studied the process of development of artistic and figurative thinking in a person and obtained a number of results in this direction.

Elliot Eisner is a famous American pedagogue and art theorist artistic in developing creative and critical thinking skills in students focused on the importance of education.

Viktor Löwenfeld is an Austrian-born teacher and art therapist who developed the theory of the stages of creative development of artistic expression in children.

Howard Gardner is an American psychologist. He is known for many of his ideas on the theory of intelligence, and is notable for his study of visual-spatial intelligence, which involves the ability of an individual to think in images and pictures.

Jerome Bruner is an American psychologist who emphasized the importance of storytelling and narrative in developing creative and imaginative thinking in students.

Ken Robinson is a British teacher and writer. It is creativity in education promoted the importance and emphasized that priority should be given to the development of creative and imaginative thinking in schoolchildren.

These researchers have contributed to the understanding of the development of artistic and figurative thinking in the individual and have greatly influenced educational theory and practice around the world.

Many researchers have studied the development of artistic and figurative thinking in future visual arts teachers.

Howard: Gardner's theory of multiple intelligences, which includes visual-spatial intelligence, has been applied to visual arts education and emphasizes the importance of teaching a wide range of artistic skills and concepts.

Betty Edwards: Edwards' book *Drawing on the Right Side of the Brain* has been influential in teaching drawing to students at all levels and emphasizes the importance of developing visual perception and imaginative thinking.

Rudolf Arnheim was a famous art teacher and psychologist who emphasized the importance of the cognitive process in the creation and development of art.

David Perkins has studied the development of artistic and creative thinking and emphasizes the importance of teaching students to think creatively and critically.

These scholars contributed to how to develop artistic and figurative thinking in future visual arts teachers and provided valuable insights into the development of effective science teaching strategies.

In artistic thinking, two tasks are solved at the same time: to feel and understand what is depicted and expressed. This requires an understanding of the expression of composite construction and the pictorial content of the composite method, as well as other components of the art form, including plasticity, texture, and color harmony.

Understanding the figurative signs that the artist communicates with us is the basis of artistic and figurative thinking. The activity of artistic thinking is required from a person to think artistically and figuratively about the objective-subjective content of the real existence expressed in the work of art.

The process of artistic thought adapts to a certain structure of the work. It is in harmony with the method, type and genre of art. But always a guide is needed for the perceiver. Guide to artistic content penetration, in order to "read" the artistic form in its entirety, helps the perceiver to perceive the idea of the work as a whole.

The following are the specific psychological aspects of the development of artistic thinking in future teachers of fine arts: - description of the psychological age of students;

- individual-psychological characteristics and types of perception of students;
- the dependence of students' intelligence, thinking, analytical abilities on various factors;
- based on individual-typological, subjective and objective psychological factors of artistic thinking;
- scheme, system, process of artistic thinking, its stages, structure, content;
- the criteria of artistic thinking
- approximate directions of artistic thinking, its versatility
- subjective and objective factors, such as individual-psychological, emotional-aesthetic, psychological-pedagogical factors in the development of artistic-image thinking in students,
- requirements for the teacher's psychological and pedagogical knowledge that forms the necessary artistic and visual thinking in students.

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